

1 **Supplementary Material**

2 This file includes:

3 Appendix 1: Supplementary Text

4 Literature Cited

5 Supplementary Tables

6 Supplementary Figures

7 Appendix 2: Data collection Protocols

8
9 Abbreviations:

10 FAD: First Appearance Datum

11 LAD: Last Appearance Datum

12 Appendix 1

13 Supplementary Text

14 1. Fossil suid species, their FADs, LADs, and ancestor-descendant relationships

15 The origins of the Plio-Pleistocene fossil suids discussed in this study can be ultimately
16 traced back to several dispersal events from Eurasia to Africa. The widely accepted
17 *Nyanzachoerus* – *Notochoerus* lineage is thought to have originated from one or several dispersal
18 events in the Late Miocene, as early *Nyanzachoerus* spp. share many morphological features
19 with tetraconodontines found in India (Cooke and Wilkinson 1978, van der Made 1998). The two
20 suine genera, *Kolpochoerus* and *Metridiochoerus*, possibly originated from separate dispersal
21 events in the Pliocene (Bishop 2011). Molecular evidence suggests that all extant African suids
22 form a single clade, with *Hylochoerus* and *Phacochoerus* being more closely related to each
23 other than either is to *Potamochoerus* (Gongora et al. 2011), which could support a single

24 dispersal event from Eurasia to Africa of a common suine ancestor. *Kolpochoerus* appears in the
25 African fossil record in the early Pliocene (ca. 5.5 Ma) with brachydont dentitions, and later
26 becomes widely distributed in eastern Africa (Souron 2012). *Metridiochoerus* appears during
27 mid-Pliocene (ca. 3.4 Ma) in the Usno and Nachukui formations (White et al. 2006), and quickly
28 becomes common in the African fossil record. It is possible that even older specimens of
29 *Metridiochoerus* were so far mistakenly attributed to the genera *Potamochoerus* or
30 *Kolpochoerus*, owing to their plesiomorphic dental morphology: see for example, discussion of
31 the Laetoli Upper Beds specimens (ca. 3.85-3.6 Ma) as possible early *Metridiochoerus* in Souron
32 (2012).

33 Figure 1 shows the stratigraphic ranges for the suid taxa present in Africa during the
34 study period (ca. 5 Ma – Present). We based our estimations on a compilation of published
35 sources and unpublished data. The following text, therefore, justifies our estimations of FAD and
36 LAD for the various suid taxa showed in Figure 1.

37

38 The genera *Nyanzachoerus* and *Notochoerus* (subfamily: Tetraconodontinae)

39 Here we only listed the widely accepted Plio-Pleistocene species in Figure 1. Note that
40 the taxonomy and phylogeny of the tetraconodontines are still debated (Boisserie et al. 2014,
41 Geraads and Bobe 2020, Reda et al. 2019). *Nyanzachoerus kanamensis* (= *Ny. pattersoni*)
42 (Boisserie et al. 2014, Geraads et al. 2013, Haile-Selassie 2009, Harris and White 1979), is well
43 represented in eastern Africa, with a radiometric FAD of ca. 4.5 Ma from the Tugen Hills and
44 possibly earlier (Bishop 1997), and with a LAD of ca. 3.2 Ma at Hadar and Shungura (Cooke
45 2007).

46 It has been well accepted that the progressive species *Ny. jaegeri* was the most probable
47 ancestor of *No. euilus* (Cooke 1985, Harris and White 1979, van der Made 1998, White and
48 Suwa 2004), although there has been some debate about whether *Ny. jaegeri* should be assigned
49 to the genus *Notochoerus* (Harris and Leakey 2003, Kullmer 1999, Reda et al. 2019).
50 *Nyanzachoerus jaegeri* is represented in multiple sites in eastern Africa, such as Lothagam,
51 Mursi, Kanapoi, and Woranso-Mille, with a FAD of ca. 4 Ma, and with a LAD of ca. 3.5 Ma
52 (Geraads and Bobe 2020, Harris and Leakey 2003, Reda et al. 2019). Its possible ancestors are
53 *Ny. tulotos* in eastern Africa from the Late Miocene (Lothagam and Middle Awash) or *Ny.*
54 *australis* from both eastern Africa (Lothagam) and South Africa (Langebaanweg), going into the
55 early Pliocene (Boisserie et al. 2014, Cooke and Hendey 1992, Haile-Selassie 2009, Harris and
56 Leakey 2003). We consider *Ny. australis* a likely ancestor of *Ny. jaegeri*, due to its intermediate
57 temporal distribution and dental metrics between *Ny. tulotos* and *Ny. jaegeri* (Boisserie et al.
58 2014, Haile-Selassie 2009). *Nyanzachoerus australis* has a FAD of ca. 5.2 Ma, and a LAD of ca.
59 4.2 Ma (Boisserie et al. 2014, Harris and Leakey 2003).

60 *Notochoerus euilus* is present in both eastern and southern Africa (Cooke 1978, Cooke
61 and Maglio 1972, Harris and White 1979, Kullmer 2008), with a FAD of ca. 3.7 Ma, from
62 Woranso-Mille (Curran and Haile-Selassie 2016) and a LAD of ca. 2.8 Ma, from the Turkana
63 Basin (Cooke 2007, Harris 1983, Harris et al. 1988). It likely diverged into two separate lineages,
64 with the more progressively hypsodont and elongated M3 morphotype known as *No. scotti*, and a
65 less elongated M3 morphotype known as *No. clarki* (Cooke 2007, White and Suwa 2004).
66 *Notochoerus scotti* is well represented in radiometrically dated sequences in the Turkana Basin
67 (Shungura, Koobi Fora, Nachukui) from ca. 2.8 Ma to 1.6 Ma (Cooke 2007, Harris 1983, Harris
68 et al. 1988). *Notochoerus clarki* is more restricted in its temporal distribution, from ca. 2.8 Ma to

69 1.9 Ma (Cooke 2007, Suwa et al. 2014, White and Suwa 2004). *Notochoerus capensis* is found
70 primarily in Makapansgat and the Vaal River Gravels (Broom 1925, Ewer 1958, Shaw 1938).
71 Harris and White (1979) described *No. capensis* as an intermediate species between *No. euilus*
72 and *No. scotti*. However, the previously assigned *No. capensis* in eastern Africa has been argued
73 to be a variant of *No. euilus* or *No. clarki* (Bishop 2011, Cooke 1993), and only recently reported
74 in Ledi-Geraru (Lazagabaster et al. 2018). We consider it possible that the geographic range of
75 *No. capensis* is more restricted to South Africa. Due to a lack of radiometric date for the South
76 African materials, we consider a FAD of ca. 3 Ma, and a LAD of ca. 2.5 Ma good estimates for
77 the temporal range of the species (Herries et al. 2013).

78

79 The genus *Kolpochoerus* (subfamily: Suinae)

80 The oldest species of the *Kolpochoerus* lineage, *K. deheinzeli*, ranges from ca. 5.5 Ma
81 to ca. 3.9 Ma (Brunet and White 2001, Haile-Selassie and Simpson 2013). It has been well
82 accepted that *K. deheinzeli* evolved progressively into *K. afarensis*, forming an anagenetic
83 lineage (Haile-Selassie and Simpson 2013). We did not include the proposed intermediate
84 chronospecies *K. millensis* (Haile-Selassie and Simpson 2013) in Figure 1, as it is not included in
85 our study.

86 *Kolpochoerus afarensis* is best known from Hadar, with a FAD at ca. 3.6 Ma (Cooke
87 1978, 1997, Fessaha 1999, Haile-Selassie and Simpson 2013). The LAD of *K. afarensis* is 2.95
88 Ma, from the upper member B of the Shungura Formation (Cooke 1997). It splits into *K. phillipi*
89 in the Afar (Souron et al. 2015), and *K. limnetes* in the Turkana Basin and other sites outside
90 Afar (Cooke 1997, Harris and White 1979). *Kolpochoerus cookei* is known only from the upper
91 Member B of the Shungura Formation, at ca. 2.95 Ma (Cooke 2007). *Kolpochoerus phillipi* is

92 found in the Middle Awash research area at ca. 2.5 Ma (Souron *et al.*, 2015) and at Ledi-Geraru
93 ca. 2.8 Ma (Lazagabaster *et al.* 2018). It is so far known only from the Afar.

94 The FAD of *K. limnetes* is ca. 2.8 Ma, from the Tulu Bor member of Koobi Fora (Harris
95 1983), and Member C of the Shungura Formation (Cooke 1997). *Kolpochoerus limnetes* splits
96 into two species ca. 1.6-1.5 Ma, giving rise to *K. paiceae* across the entire African continent
97 except for the Turkana Basin, and a population that was endemic to the Turkana Basin, which
98 eventually became a different species. The latter is here referred to as *K. aff. paiceae*. We
99 consider *K. "olduvaiensis"* a synonym of *K. paiceae* (Bibi *et al.* 2018; Souron, unpublished). The
100 transition between the late stage of *K. limnetes* and early *K. paiceae* in eastern Africa is best
101 represented in the Konso Formation, between 1.75 Ma and 1.45 Ma (Suwa *et al.* 2014). The
102 LADs of both *K. paiceae* and *K. aff. paiceae* are not very well documented. The gray color
103 gradient towards their LADs in Figure 1 of the main manuscript reflects this uncertainty. The
104 "Shaw & Cooke 30" specimen is from the Younger Gravel C Member of the Vaal River gravels,
105 with an age range of 0.6 Ma to 0.2 Ma (Helgren 1977).

106 The FAD of *Kolpochoerus majus* could go as far back as ca. 1.9 Ma from the Konso
107 Formation (Suwa *et al.* 2014), although the taxonomy is still being debated. The Konso material
108 shows several intermediate characters between the older *K. phillipi* and the younger material
109 typically assigned to *K. majus*. Suwa *et al.* (2014) referred to the material as *K. cf. majus* to
110 reflect this uncertainty. The LAD of *K. majus* could be as late as ca. 0.1 Ma from the Wasiriya
111 Beds, Rusinga Island (Faith 2014, Tryon *et al.* 2012, but see Lazagabaster *et al.* 2021 for an
112 alternative taxonomic identification). It has been well accepted that *Hylochoerus* diverged from
113 *K. majus* (Cooke and Wilkinson 1978, Geraads 2004, Harris and White 1979, Souron *et al.*
114 2015). However, when exactly the split occurred is still enigmatic, due to very scant and poorly

115 dated fossil evidence for *Hylochoerus* (Assefa et al. 2008, Harris and White 1979, Lazagabaster
116 et al. 2021).

117

118 The genus *Metridiochoerus* (subfamily: Suinae)

119 *Metridiochoerus* first occurs in the African fossil record in the Usno and Nachukui
120 formations, ca. 3.4 Ma (White et al. 2006). Due to the limited amount of fossil material available
121 for this early member, we have taken a conservative approach and decided to use
122 *Metridiochoerus* sp. as its designation, although some scholars have attributed *Metridiochoerus*
123 specimens of similar antiquity to *M. andrewsi* (Harris et al. 1988). *Metridiochoerus shawi* is
124 primarily known from South African sites, except for one possible specimen from Shungura
125 (Cooke 1993, 2005). We adopted an age estimate of 2.7 Ma for the Makapansgat material used
126 in this study (Herries et al. 2013). We consider *M. shawi* a good representative of the dental
127 morphotype of early *Metridiochoerus* found in eastern Africa. “*Kolpochoerus*” *phacochoeroides*
128 is only reported from northern Africa (Geraads 2002, 2004). Despite its current taxonomic
129 designation, it displays several craniomandibular and dental features that align it better with the
130 genus *Metridiochoerus* (Cherin et al. 2018, Souron 2012, 2015), which is the reason why we
131 placed it under the genus *Metridiochoerus* in Figure 1 of the main manuscript. Its systematics is
132 still work in progress.

133 *Metridiochoerus andrewsi* is well documented in the Turkana Basin (Cooke 2007, Cooke
134 and Maglio 1972, Harris 1983, Harris et al. 1988, Harris and White 1979), including the
135 transition between advanced *M. andrewsi* and more derived *M. compactus* (Cooke 2007, Harris
136 1983, Harris and White 1979). We consider that the two species were chronospecies of a single
137 lineage, with the transition taking place ca. 1.6 Ma. The youngest confirmed *M. compactus*

138 comes from Olduvai Bed IV, ca. 0.78 Ma (Gilbert 2008, White 1995), but they possibly also
139 occurred in younger deposits (e.g., Cruz-Uribe 1983, Frost et al. 2012, Geraads 2002, McKee et
140 al. 1995).

141 The fossil record of both *M. modestus* and *M. hopwoodi* are sporadic compared to the
142 other *Metridiochoerus* spp. (e.g., Bishop 2011, Cooke 1993, Harris 1983, Harris and White 1979,
143 Suwa et al. 2014). For this reason, we estimated their FADs and LADs with large margins of
144 uncertainty (Fig. 1), from ca. 2.1 Ma to ca. 0.7 Ma (Bishop 2011, Harris et al. 1988, White and
145 Harris 1977).

146

147 The genus *Phacochoerus* (subfamily: Suinae)

148 The oldest certain *Phacochoerus* specimens come from the Daka Member of Middle
149 Awash, at ca. 1 Ma (Gilbert 2008) although there are oldest reports based on isolated teeth from
150 uncertain stratigraphic contexts (Cooke 2007, Harris and White 1979). This pushes the possible
151 divergence of *Phacochoerus* from *M. modestus* to at least between 1.5 Ma and 1 Ma. Species-
152 level taxonomy of Pleistocene *Phacochoerus* is not a focus of this study and is therefore not
153 discussed here.

154

155 2. Wear simulation using micro-CT data

156 The sequences of virtually simulated “occlusal surfaces” were generated using the
157 “oblique slice” function in the AVIZO software (Ver. 7.1). We adjusted the slices perpendicular
158 to the growth axis of the second pair of pillars for consistency purposes. For species that have
159 mesially curved pillars, we used the cervical half of the second pair as our reference for
160 positioning the slices. We decided not to adjust individual slices to be perpendicular to the

161 curved pillars because changing the slice angle would make the process less repeatable and could
162 potentially introduce more error. Detailed processes of wear simulation are illustrated in
163 Appendix 2.

164 To evaluate the effects of micro-CT image resolution on the measurements of this study,
165 we performed a fidelity test using one occlusal photograph of *Metridiochoerus andrewsi* and
166 decimated the pixel count of the image to seven different resolutions using *Adobe Photoshop*
167 *CS6* (Supplementary Fig. 3). The results suggest that image resolutions higher than 5.25 pixels
168 per mm (voxel size of 0.19 mm or smaller) produce consistent measurements. All of our micro-
169 CT images were performed at voxel resolutions higher than 5.25 pixels per mm (Supplementary
170 Table 2). Therefore, we are confident that the scanning resolution of micro-CT should have
171 minimal effects on the results of our analyses and our interpretations.

172

173 3. Measurement of dental wear

174 Dentine exposure ratio (*DER*) as a proxy for dental wear follows the principle that the
175 more dentine is exposed on the occlusal surface, the more cumulative dental material is lost in
176 the wear process. This principle has been used in similar ways in various dental wear scoring
177 systems in human dentition (Molnar 1971, Murphy 1959, Smith 1984). One of the most
178 substantial limitations of using a scoring system in suid M3s is that the number of talon/talonid
179 pillars varies both among fossil suid lineages and also between early and late members of the
180 same lineage (Cooke and Maglio 1972, Harris and White 1979). As a result, it is difficult to
181 apply the same scoring system to different species. Using a universal index permits comparison
182 across species with different crown lengths and provides a continuous measurement instead of a
183 discrete number to represent dental wear progression.

184 Our proxy for dental wear progression (*DER*) only quantifies the geometric relationship
185 between enamel and dentine, which not only depends on the number of cusp(id)s/pillars but also
186 on the individual shape of the cusp(id)s/pillars (e.g., being conical or columnar). When
187 comparing the variation patterns of occlusal traits among species, the pillar/cusp(id) shape is
188 assumed to follow the same pattern (along the same *DER* axis), while different lineages do
189 exhibit different pillar shapes (Harris and White 1979, Kullmer 1999). Supplementary Figure 4
190 demonstrates that dentine index (x-axis) seems to follow a logarithmic growth relationship with
191 the height of the crown (y-axis) in most fossil suid species: $y = a * \ln(x + b) + c$. Note that in
192 species with the highest crowns, this relationship is approaching linearity. The shape of the curve
193 can be explained by two parameters: the growth parameter (*a*: “slope” of the curve) and the
194 position parameters (*b*: “curvature” of the curve). The slope of the curve seems to correspond
195 well with the degree of hypsodonty of the crown, with earlier species displaying lower slopes
196 than later species. The difference in the slopes between *Kolpochoerus* spp. and the other two
197 genera are also consistent with previous observations that *Kolpochoerus* spp. have much lower
198 crowns. The growth parameter in this relationship may also serve as a quantitative measurement
199 of hypsodonty but we did not explore this relationship further due to the small number of
200 specimens available. One limitation of this method is that it cannot measure the amount of
201 enamel that is removed before dentine is exposed (Elgart 2010, Mayhall and Kageyama 1997).
202 However, this issue would have little effect on our interpretation of the results since the amount
203 that is worn before dentine is exposed constitutes a minuscule proportion of the entire dental
204 wear trajectory in most herbivores with moderate crown heights, which applies to all the extant
205 and fossil suid specimens included in this study.

206

207 4. Image processing using Adobe Photoshop and Fiji

208 We decided to manually process the images due to the variable contrasts between dental
209 tissues of fossil specimens in micro-CT images. The lack of contrast between enamel and dentine
210 is especially notable for fossil specimens from the Koobi Fora Formation. For example, we
211 selected 11 specimens to be transported to South Africa to be scanned, but only 7 produced
212 useable contrast for manual processing. There was one more scan that we obtained from our
213 colleagues, but it also suffered from low contrast and was not included in this study. Because of
214 the variable contrasts, we were not able to use consistent contrast cutoffs for enamel or dentine.
215 Manual processing also allows for informed reconstruction of simulated occlusal surfaces, for
216 example, when cracks are present in fossil specimens. Detailed processes of wear simulation are
217 illustrated in Appendix 2.

218

219 5. Sources of error

220 Multiple sources of error could be introduced in the various steps of image processing
221 (see Appendix 2). Here we discuss three major sources of error that could influence the results.
222 Two major sources of error are inter- and intra-observer errors in the steps of manual image
223 processing using Adobe Photoshop. The other source is in the steps of generating virtually
224 simulated occlusal surfaces from micro-CT images. Image processing using Fiji software is
225 quantitative and consistent across all observers, which should introduce minimal error.

226 In this project, three individuals (J. Kolasa, A. Pisano, and M. Marazanof) participated in
227 the manual processing of micro-CT images (Appendix 3). We evaluated both inter-observer and
228 intra-observer errors by repeating the entire data collection process on selected specimens. In the
229 first set of error estimation, we evaluated inter-observer error by independently performing data

230 collection among the three participants, using the entire slice sequence of extant *Sus scrofa*
231 specimen P18 (Supplementary Table 1, and Supplementary Table 2 for specimen information).
232 This also allowed us to investigate how error is correlated with each measurement, in order to
233 systematically construct confidence intervals around the data points. The measurements are
234 plotted in Supplementary Figure 5, and the results of inter-observer errors are reported in
235 Supplementary Table 5. We first plotted the absolute inter-observer error against each
236 measurement and used a linear model to investigate whether there is a potential correlation for
237 each measurement. We found that the absolute error for *EDBI* positively correlates with *EDBI*
238 (linear regression, $p = 0.003$, adjusted $R^2 = 0.31$, Supplementary Table 3). This indicates that the
239 confidence interval of *EDBI* measurements should be scaled with *EDBI* values. In comparison,
240 the linear trends are not significant for the absolute error of *DER* and enamel thickness (*ET*,
241 Supplementary Table 3), although the p -value for *DER* approached significance ($p = 0.052$). In
242 order to construct our confidence interval using the highest margin of error in *EDBI*, we used an
243 arbitrary line as our linear error predictor, in which all the error points plot lower than this
244 artificial line for each measurement (Supplementary Fig. 1, Supplementary Table 4). For *EDBI*
245 and *ET*, we opted to report a fixed error margin for the inter-observer error. The inter-observer
246 error analysis formed the baseline of our error estimations. Other sources of error were compared
247 to these estimates first, then the higher error margin was chosen to construct the confidence
248 interval of our reported measurements.

249 In the second set of error estimation, we investigated intra-observer error by using KNM-
250 ER 2193 and KNM-ER 1777 as test subjects and repeated our data collection protocol twice on
251 four different slices in each specimen, respectively (Supplementary Fig. 6). This analysis was
252 performed by A. Pisano. We chose these two fossil specimens specifically because they display

253 the highest *EDBI* values, which might be associated with larger error margins than those
254 discussed previously. We found that for the error associated with *EDBI*, the inter-observer error
255 margin was consistently higher than the intra-observer error. However, the error associated with
256 *DER* and *ET* in this analysis were higher than the inter-observer error margins (Supplementary
257 Tables S6 and S7). We decided to adopt the highest margins, with 0.048 as the error margin for
258 *DER*, and 0.136 as the error margin for *ET*, as our updated confidence limits for further analyses.

259 The error associated with generating oblique slices from micro-CT images can come
260 from inconsistent angles of the simulated occlusal surfaces to the growth axis of the second pair
261 of pillars. We estimated this source of error by arbitrarily tilting the oblique slice relative to the
262 reference slice along two different axes. The first set of slices were tilted along the buccolingual
263 axis relative to the reference plane, which generated simulated occlusal surfaces at an angle to
264 the growth axis of the second pair of pillars from the lateral view (Supplementary Fig. 7). The
265 second set of slices were tilted along the mesiodistal axis, which generated simulated occlusal
266 surfaces at an angle to the growth axis of the second pair of pillars from the mesial view
267 (Supplementary Fig. 7). We selected one slice position and compared the values of the tilted
268 slice relative to the reference slice. Tilting the slice angle does change the values of *DER*, *EDBI*,
269 and *ET* (Supplementary Table S8). Notably, the largest deviation of *EDBI* is 7.3 % from the
270 original value, which is higher than the intra-observer margin discussed above (Supplementary
271 Table S7). We decided to use this percentage error as our updated slope for the linear error
272 estimation model in the construction of confidence limits, as reported in Table 1.

273 In order to test the fidelity of our protocol, we also collected data on two independently
274 extracted series of slices from the same specimen (AaO-3932, UM3). Detailed information about
275 the specimen is listed in Supplementary Table S1. Series 1 was extracted by D. Yang; series 2

276 was extracted by A. Souron. Data were collected by J. Kolasa on both series (Appendix 3). When
277 plotted in the wear space, the two series show substantial overlap in both *EDBI* and *ET*
278 (Supplementary Fig. 8). The only exception comes from the peak *EDBI* value of series 2, which
279 falls outside the confidence interval of series 1. In general, the results demonstrate that our
280 workflow displays good fidelity between users in setting the slice plane perpendicular to the
281 growth axis of the specimen.

282 To confidently interpret our results, we constructed a confidence interval around our
283 reported data points using the largest margins of error as our confidence limits. The confidence
284 interval is constructed in the form of a shaded polygon around a specific data series both in the
285 Results section of the main manuscript and this supplementary document.

286

287 6. Examining intra-specific variation in occlusal traits using extant suids

288 Due to the limited number of fossil specimens available in our analysis, we evaluated the
289 sensitivity of our methods using extant wild boars (*Sus scrofa*) and extant warthogs
290 (*Phacochoerus africanus*). We quantified intra-individual variation between associated pairs of
291 upper and lower M3s of the same individuals of both species, as well as intra-specific variation
292 among individuals in *Sus scrofa*.

293 The *Sus scrofa* specimens came from a single population of wild boars that were
294 collected by hunters from August to November 2017, near Tautavel, southwestern France. Sex
295 identification was based on observations of the morphology and size of the canines and the
296 supra-canine flange. Fresh boar heads were transported to PACEA, Université de Bordeaux, and
297 prepared into osteological specimens. Defleshing was performed using knives and scalpels, then
298 via slow simmering in water. After the specimens were completely dried, one associated pair of

299 upper and lower third molars was extracted from each of the three juvenile individuals (third
300 molars still in alveoli) using a Dremel rotary tool with a circular precision saw. The specimens
301 (P12, P14, and P18, Supplementary Table 1) are stored at the laboratory PACEA, Université de
302 Bordeaux, France. The *Phacochoerus africanus* specimens MRAC-2287 and MRAC-6187 are
303 housed in the Musée royal de l'Afrique centrale, Belgium (Supplementary Table 1), and were
304 micro-CT scanned by Ana Rosa Gomez Cano. The Souron1 specimen has no provenience
305 information. It was donated to A. Souron as part of a laboratory collection (details published in
306 Yang et al. 2020). It is housed in the laboratory PACEA, Université de Bordeaux, and was
307 micro-CT scanned at the same facility.

308 Within the same tooth position among the three *Sus scrofa* individuals, the wear
309 trajectory of enamel complexity and thickness measurements show the same patterns
310 (Supplementary Fig. 9). Between upper and lower M3s of the same individual, there is a slight
311 difference in the wear trajectory of upper and lower M3s in that the upper M3 display
312 consistently higher enamel complexity at the peak of the trajectory. In comparison, the wear
313 trajectory of enamel thickness shows similar patterns between upper and lower M3s, except for
314 the first slice in which the enamel thickness of lower M3s is consistently smaller.

315 Similar to the *Sus scrofa* material, the associated pair of upper and lower M3s of
316 *Phacochoerus africanus* shows overlapping values in both enamel complexity and thickness (see
317 Fig. 6). However, whether upper and lower M3s differ in *Phacochoerus africanus* is still
318 inconclusive, due to the limited number of specimens available in this study (two pairs of
319 associated upper and lower M3s). Since the patterns among different individuals are near
320 identical among selected extant suids, we are confident that our method can produce consistent
321 results among individuals of the same population. We consider that our method is sensitive

322 enough to distinguish minor differences in enamel complexity and thickness between associated
323 upper and lower M3s within the same individual. This also suggests caution when pooling upper
324 and lower M3s in the analysis. Nevertheless, the observed differences between upper and lower
325 M3s are generally smaller than the differences between selected specimens that represent
326 different species/chronospecies, which provides confidence to our interpretations.

327

328 7. Comparing wear trajectories in upper and lower M3s of selected fossil suid species

329 Our fossil sample size is small due to the limited availability of micro-CT scans of fossil
330 suid M3s. In order to confidently pool upper and lower M3s when comparing fossil taxa, we
331 compared occlusal traits in upper and lower third molars using specimens from the same
332 geographic origin and stratigraphic member, representing different individuals of the same
333 population. We used fossil specimens of *M. shawi* and *No. scotti* as they are the only fossil taxa
334 of which both upper and lower M3s have been micro-CT scanned in our dataset.

335 In *M. shawi*, upper and lower M3s of the same population show minor differences in their
336 occlusal traits (see also Fig. 3). From the two specimens plotted in Supplementary Figure 10, the
337 lower M3 displays slightly higher maximum values in enamel complexity and lower values in
338 enamel thickness than the upper M3. The wear trajectories are almost the same for both enamel
339 complexity and thickness and the values fall within the error margins of each other. Based on
340 this pattern, for the *Metridiochoerus* tooth type, we consider that the upper and lower M3s of the
341 same species could be pooled due to the similarity of their dental wear trajectories. The results
342 are consistent with previous work comparing the occlusal appearance between upper and lower
343 M3s of *Metridiochoerus* spp. in that they generally display minor differences in size and occlusal
344 enamel pattern (Harris and White 1979, Kullmer 1999).

345 In comparison, *No. scotti* displays major differences in the wear trajectories of both
346 enamel complexity and thickness. The lower M3 shows higher maximum enamel complexity and
347 lower enamel thickness. The higher maximum complexity is likely associated with a higher
348 number of paired pillars in the lower M3 (8 vs 7 in the UM3). The results are consistent with
349 previous work comparing upper and lower M3s of *No. scotti* in that upper and lower M3s have
350 distinct wear patterns on the pillars (Harris and White 1979). The other source of variation in the
351 observed pattern could come from the potentially larger amount of temporal variation
352 represented between the two specimens from the Koobi Fora Formation. Based on these
353 observations, we concluded that the upper and lower M3s of *No. scotti* could not be pooled due
354 to the different trajectories in occlusal traits between upper and lower M3s as dental wear
355 progresses.

356

357 8. Similarities among proxies of enamel complexity

358 The three proxies of enamel complexity (structural density “*D*”, occlusal enamel length
359 index “*OEL*”, and enamel-dentine boundary index “*EDBF*”) share substantial similarities but are
360 associated with slightly different assumptions. Structural density “*D*” (Schmidt-Kittler 1984) is
361 expressed as:

$$362 \quad D = \frac{L^2}{4\pi F} \quad (S1)$$

363 where *L* = enamel length of a single pillar, *F* = occlusal area of a single pillar.

364 Occlusal enamel length index “*OEL*” (Famoso et al. 2013) is expressed as:

$$365 \quad OEI = \frac{OEL}{\sqrt{OccA}} \quad (S2)$$

366 where *OEL* = occlusal enamel length, *OccA* = occlusal area, as in equation (1) of the main

367 manuscript.

368 *EDBI* is expressed in equation (2) of the main manuscript as $EDBI = \frac{EDBL}{\sqrt{OccA}}$.

369 It is clear that the three proxies describe a similar geometric relationship between the
370 occlusal enamel band and the occlusal area. In fact, when the tooth only has one single enamel
371 enclosure (e.g., in rodents), D can be expressed as $OEI^2/4\pi$, following a quadratic relationship
372 with OEI . Because both OEL and $OccA$ are always positive values, D and OEI are positively
373 correlated. The difference between these two proxies is mainly in their assumptions: D quantifies
374 the degree of enamel folding within a single enamel enclosure (as in a single pillar); while OEI
375 does not rely on this assumption. In fact, some studies have expanded the use of D in occlusal
376 patterns that have multiple enamel enclosures (Gailer et al. 2016, Gailer and Kaiser 2014). In this
377 case, D and OEI follow the same mathematical relationship as described before. Similarly, $EDBI$
378 should be positively correlated with OEI , as occlusal enamel length positively correlates with
379 enamel-dentine boundary length. Like OEI , it does not rely on the assumption that the length of
380 enamel band is within a single enamel enclosure. Therefore, it is reasonable to assume that $EDBI$
381 is also positively correlated with D when D is applied to multiple enamel enclosures.

382

383 9. Comparison between micro-CT simulated and “real world” occlusal surfaces

384 To further test how comparable the simulated occlusal surfaces are with “real world”
385 occlusal wear patterns, we provided a preliminary comparison between data collected from
386 occlusal photographs of selected specimens from the Koobi Fora Formation (Appendix 3) and
387 the reference specimens in Figures 4 and 5. We used the same manual processing protocol to
388 generate DER , $EDBI$, and ET values and plotted the results in Supplementary Figure 11. We
389 observed that the DER and $EDBI$ values generated from occlusal photographs fall within the
390 confidence limits of the reference specimens. However, assuming that the DER values are

391 unbiased compared to the reference specimens, the *ET* values generated from occlusal
392 photographs seem to be lower than those of the reference specimens. This could be due to a
393 consistent bias between the two methods, or simply the intra-specific variation that is not
394 captured by the reference specimens. One possibility to explain the difference is associated with
395 the observation that the outer enamel rim of “real world” occlusal surfaces are often rounded due
396 to dental macro wear. This may lead to an underestimation of both the occlusal area and the
397 occlusal enamel area, potentially affecting both *DER* and *ET* systematically. On the other hand,
398 *EDBI* being independent to size, it should be less sensitive to such biases. The other possibility to
399 explain this potential bias is associated with the consistency of placing the physical scale within
400 the photographs. When the digital scale is placed closer to the camera than the occlusal
401 photograph (which happens sometimes), the scale would occupy a larger number of pixels than
402 the true number. As a result, the number of pixels represented by the enamel thickness on the
403 occlusal surface would be smaller than the true number, thus, explaining the bias. Admittedly,
404 this comparison is at a small scale and was not carried out systematically to quantify all potential
405 biases. Nonetheless, the results demonstrate that the data from the simulated occlusal surfaces
406 are generally in good agreement with real world occlusal surfaces.

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586

587 Supplementary Tables

588 Supplementary Table 1. List of specimens micro-CT scanned in this study; age estimates come
 589 from the following references: Bobe (2002), Domínguez-Rodrigo et al. (2007), Geraads (2002),
 590 (Harris 1983), Helgren (1977), Herries et al. (2013), McDougall et al. (2012); *Met.* =
 591 *Metridiochoerus*; *Not.* = *Notochoerus*; *Kol.* = *Kolpochoerus*; *Pha.* = *Phacochoerus*; *Pota.* =
 592 *Potamochoerus*; UM3 = upper M3; LM3 = lower M3; Lt. = left; Rt. = right; DR Congo =
 593 Democratic Republic of Congo.

Specimen	Site	Member	Species	Age	Element
KNM-ER 2193	East Turkana	KBS	<i>Met. compactus</i>	~1.6 Ma	UM3
KNM-ER 2194	East Turkana	KBS	<i>Met. andrewsi</i>	~1.8 Ma	LM3
M.1924	Makapansgat	Member 3	<i>Met. shawi</i>	~2.7 Ma	UM3
M.2072	Makapansgat	Member 3	<i>Met. shawi</i>	~2.7 Ma	LM3
M.2073	Makapansgat	Member 3	<i>Met. shawi</i>	~2.7 Ma	UM3
M.2081	Makapansgat	Member 3	<i>Met. shawi</i>	~2.7 Ma	LM3
M.8371	Makapansgat	Member 3	<i>Met. shawi</i>	~2.7 Ma	LM3
AaO-3932	Ahl al Oughlam	n/a	" <i>Kol.</i> " <i>phacochoeroides</i>	~2.3 Ma	UM3
KNM-ER 3502	East Turkana	Upper Burgi	<i>Not. scotti</i>	~2 Ma	UM3
KNM-ER 1777	East Turkana	Upper Burgi	<i>Not. scotti</i>	~2 Ma	LM3
KNM-ER 2779	East Turkana	Tulu Bor	<i>Not. euilus</i>	~2.8 Ma	LM3
Shaw & Cooke 30	Vaal River	Younger Gravel C	<i>Kol. paiceae</i>	~0.4 Ma	LM3
KNM-ER 2189	East Turkana	KBS	<i>Kol. limnetes</i>	~1.8 Ma	LM3
KNM-ER 2778	East Turkana	Tulu Bor	<i>Kol. limnetes</i>	~2.8 Ma	LM3
P12	France	-	<i>Sus scrofa</i>	Extant	Rt. UM3 and LM3
P14	France	-	<i>Sus scrofa</i>	Extant	Rt. UM3 and LM3

P18	France	-	<i>Sus scrofa</i>	Extant	Lt. UM3 and LM3
MRAC 2287	DR Congo	-	<i>Pha. africanus</i>	Extant	Rt. UM3 and LM3
MRAC 6187	DR Congo	-	<i>Pha. africanus</i>	Extant	Rt. UM3 and LM3
Souron1	n/a	-	<i>Pha. africanus</i>	Extant	UM3
MBMA7008	Lake Eyasi, Tanzania	n/a	<i>Pota. sp.</i>	~0.2 Ma	LM3

594

595 Supplementary Table 2. Information on micro-CT scans and virtual slices. Res. = resolution.

Specimen	Voxel Res. (vx/mm)	# of slices
KNM-ER 2193	12.0	16
KNM-ER 2194	11.7	13
M.1924	20.7	10
M.2072	17.0	13
M.2073	15.3	12
M.2081	14.0	13
M.8371	13.0	12
AaO-3932	27.9	11
KNM-ER 3502	6.5	12
KNM-ER 1777	6.8	16
KNM-ER 2779	11.1	13
Shaw & Cooke 30	10.1	12
KNM-ER 2189	13.8	13
KNM-ER 2778	16.6	14
P12	50.0	8 each
P14	50.0	8 each
P18	50.0	8 each
MRAC 2287	11.6	12 each
MRAC 6187	11.6	12 each
Souron1	17.3	8
MBMA008	20.0	8

596

597 Supplementary Table 3. Examining potential linear relationships between the measurements and
 598 their associated inter-observer error; original error is reported in Supplementary Table 5 with the
 599 linear trends plotted in Supplementary Figure 5; err = error; Std. = standard; DER = Dentine
 600 Exposure Ratio; EDBI = Enamel-Dentine Boundary Index; ET = Enamel Thickness.

Model	Adjusted R^2	Intercept [Std. err]	p -value	Slope [Std. err]	p -value
err-DER ~ DER	0.125	0.0032 [0.0008]	0.001	5.25×10^{-3} [2.56×10^{-3}]	0.052
err-EDBI ~ EDBI	0.913	0.075 [0.051]	0.155	0.0298 [0.009]	0.003
err-ET ~ ET	0.908	-0.014 [0.053]	0.786	0.039 [0.039]	0.323

601

602 Supplementary Table 4. Error models arbitrarily selected for the inter-observer error analysis; the
 603 models are also plotted in Supplementary Figure 1. Note that error associated with DER and
 604 EDBI have slopes of zero, being constant numbers, while error associated with EDBI is modeled
 605 to increase as the measurement increases. err = error; DER = Dentine Exposure Ratio; EDBI =
 606 Enamel-Dentine Boundary Index; ET = Enamel Thickness.

Model	Intercept	Slope
err-DER ~ DER	0.011	0
err-EDBI ~ EDBI	0.12	0.055
err-ET ~ ET	0.103	0

607

608

609 Supplementary Table 5. Estimating inter-observer error using the entire sequence of *Sus scrofa*
610 specimen P18; original data are plotted in Figure 5 and can be found in Appendix 3; note that the
611 first slice consistently displays the highest percentage error but low absolute error; Observers: M.
612 = M. Marazanof; K. = J. Kolasa; P. = A. Pisano; err = error; DER = Dentine Exposure Ratio;
613 EDBI = Enamel-Dentine Boundary Index; ET = Enamel Thickness.

Observer pair	Slice	err-DER	% err-DER	err-EDBI	% err-EDBI	err-ET	% err-ET
K. - M.	1	0.004	26.4	0.05	6.9	0.01	0.7
K. - M.	2	-0.002	-6.3	-0.13	-10.6	0.05	3.3
K. - M.	3	-0.007	-10.4	-0.23	-6.9	0.10	6.4
K. - M.	4	-0.003	-2.2	-0.19	-3.3	0.04	2.8
K. - M.	5	-0.009	-3.9	-0.25	-3.6	0.05	4.1
K. - M.	6	0.004	1.1	-0.24	-3.1	0.03	2.5
K. - M.	7	-0.004	-1.0	0.01	0.1	-0.01	-0.8
K. - M.	8	-0.007	-1.0	-0.30	-4.7	0.09	7.2
M. - P.	1	-0.005	-45.6	-0.16	-30.9	-0.04	-3.1
M. - P.	2	0.001	3.6	0.03	2.1	0.00	0.3
M. - P.	3	0.006	8.2	-0.04	-1.2	-0.01	-0.8
M. - P.	4	-0.002	-1.4	-0.19	-3.5	-0.04	-3.2
M. - P.	5	0.004	1.8	-0.26	-3.9	-0.01	-0.5
M. - P.	6	-0.011	-3.1	-0.28	-3.7	0.01	1.0
M. - P.	7	0.002	0.4	-0.35	-4.4	0.03	2.5
M. - P.	8	0.003	0.5	-0.39	-6.2	-0.06	-5.3
P. - K.	1	0.001	6.7	0.11	17.9	0.03	2.3

Observer pair	Slice	err-DER	% err-DER	err-EDBI	% err-EDBI	err-ET	% err-ET
P. - K.	2	0.001	2.5	0.11	7.6	-0.06	-3.7
P. - K.	3	0.001	1.3	0.27	7.6	-0.09	-6.0
P. - K.	4	0.005	3.5	0.37	6.4	0.00	0.3
P. - K.	5	0.005	2.0	0.51	7.1	-0.05	-3.8
P. - K.	6	0.007	2.0	0.51	6.5	-0.04	-3.6
P. - K.	7	0.002	0.5	0.34	4.1	-0.02	-1.7
P. - K.	8	-0.010	-1.6	0.09	1.4	0.02	2.0

614

615

616 Supplementary Table 6. Summary of inter-observer error using KNM-ER 2193 as a test subject.
 617 DER = Dentine Exposure Ratio; EDBI = Enamel-Dentine Boundary Index; ET = Enamel
 618 Thickness; asterisks (*) indicate error that is modeled to be linearly correlated with EDBI, using
 619 the relationship described in Supplementary Table 4. The largest margin of error for each
 620 parameter is bolded.

	Measurement	DER	EDBI	ET
KNM-ER 2193-4	Reference	0.245	11.44	1.217
	Repeated	0.225	11.51	1.293
	Error	-0.020	+0.07	+0.076
	Inter-observer margin	0.011	*0.76	0.103
	% Error		+0.6%	+5.9%
KNM-ER 2193-7	Reference	0.315	13.79	1.221
	Repeated	0.284	13.66	1.307
	Error	-0.031	-0.13	+0.086
	Inter-observer margin	0.011	*0.89	0.103
	% Error		-1.0%	+6.6%
KNM-ER 2193-10	Reference	0.343	15.29	1.176
	Repeated	0.324	15.33	1.217
	Error	-0.019	+0.04	+0.041
	Inter-observer margin	0.011	*0.97	0.103
	% Error		+0.2%	+3.4%
KNM-ER 2193-16	Reference	0.467	15.50	1.123
	Repeated	0.436	15.25	1.254
	Error	-0.031	-0.25	+0.131
	Inter-observer margin	0.011	*0.98	0.103
	% Error		-1.6%	+10.4%

621

622 Supplementary Table 7. Summary of intra-observer error using KNM-ER 1777 as a test subject.
 623 DER = Dentine Exposure Ratio; EDBI = Enamel-Dentine Boundary Index; ET = Enamel
 624 Thickness; asterisks (*) indicate error that is modeled to be linearly correlated with EDBI, using
 625 the relationship described in Supplementary Table 4. The largest margin of error for each
 626 parameter is bolded.

	Measurement	DER	EDBI	ET
KNM-ER 1777-2	Reference	0.183	10.86	1.281
	Repeated	0.178	11.19	1.286
	Error	-0.005	+0.33	+0.005
	Inter-observer margin	0.011	*0.73	0.103
	% Error		+2.7%	+0.4%
KNM-ER 1777-6	Reference	0.266	16.43	1.154
	Repeated	0.232	16.00	1.255
	Error	-0.034	-0.43	+0.101
	Inter-observer margin	0.011	*1.03	0.103
	% Error		-2.6%	+8.6%
KNM-ER 1777-12	Reference	0.359	18.08	1.106
	Repeated	0.311	17.62	1.225
	Error	-0.048	-0.46	+0.119
	Inter-observer margin	0.011	*1.13	0.103
	% Error		-2.9%	+9.7%
KNM-ER 1777-15	Reference	0.427	17.59	1.083
	Repeated	0.385	16.96	1.219
	Error	-0.042	-0.63	+0.136
	Inter-observer margin	0.011	*1.10	0.103
	% Error		-3.7%	+11.1%

627

628 Supplementary Table 8. Results of potential error associated with the sensitivity test on slice
 629 angle, using arbitrarily tilted slices of fossil specimen M.2072, as in Supplementary Figure 7.
 630 The largest margin of error for each parameter is bolded. Note that Angle 1 produces a higher
 631 margin of error associated with EDBI. The percentage error of 7.3 % was then used as the
 632 updated slope for our linear error estimation model (see Table 2). DER = Dentine Exposure
 633 Ratio; EDBI = Enamel-Dentine Boundary Index; ET = Enamel Thickness.

Measurement	DER	EDBI	ET
Reference	0.246	9.52	1.54
Angle 1	0.228	8.82	1.588
Error	-0.018	-0.70	0.048
Intra-observer margin	0.048	0.65	0.136
% Error	-7.90%	-7.30%	3.10%
Angle 2	0.277	8.89	1.555
Error	0.031	-0.63	0.015
Intra-observer margin	0.048	0.65	0.136
% Error	3.97%	-6.70%	1.00%
Angle 3	0.26	9.2	1.537
Error	0.014	-0.32	-0.003
Intra-observer margin	0.048	0.65	0.136
% Error	4.23%	-3.40%	-0.20%

634

635 Supplementary Figures

636

637 Supplementary Figure 1. Linear models for inter-observer error associated with each
 638 measurement; colored symbols represent different inter-observer pairs; solid lines represent the
 639 best fit lines of the linear models with *p*-values; dashed lines represent the highest margin of
 640 error for the measurements; Err. = error; K = J. Kolasa; M = M. Marazanof; P = A. Pisano; DER
 641 = Dentine Exposure Ratio; EDBI = Enamel-Dentine Boundary Index; ET = Enamel Thickness.

642

643
 644 Supplementary Figure 2. Comparing the correlations between third molar elongation (marked by
 645 the number of main pillars, Table 1) and relative occlusal enamel thickness (RET) as ET (Fig. 5)
 646 divided by the width of the tooth in three studied fossil suid lineages; shaded areas represent
 647 confidence limits of data points \pm the error of ET (Table 2) divided by the width of the tooth;
 648 DER = Dentine Exposure Ratio; Ma = mega-annum.

650
 651 Supplementary Figure 3. Results of the fidelity test on the effects of scanning resolution on the
 652 parameters of this study. Voxel densities higher than 5.25 vx/mm are more likely to produce
 653 consistent results. DER = Dentine Exposure Ratio; EDBI = Enamel-Dentine Boundary Index.

654

655

656 Supplementary Figure 4. The relationship between micro-CT slice depth (crown height) and

657 DER in fossil suid specimens analyzed in this study.

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659

660 Supplementary Figure 5. Comparison of measurements performed by the three participants in
 661 data collection on *Sus scrofa* specimen P18 LM3. Raw data are reported in Appendix 3. The data
 662 points show reasonable clustering, indicating the repeatability of the methods. DER = Dentine
 663 Exposure Ratio; EDBI = Enamel-Dentine Boundary Index; ET = Enamel Thickness.

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666

667 Supplementary Figure 6. Intra-observer errors using two fossil suid specimens (KNM-ER 2193

668 and KNM-ER 1777); DER = Dentine Exposure Ratio; EDBI = Enamel-Dentine Boundary Index;

669 ET = Enamel Thickness.

670

671
 672 Supplementary Figure 7. Investigating errors associated with slice angle; tilted slices are
 673 referenced to the original slice angle in two different axes and from two different views; for the
 674 buccolingual axis, the slices were tilted two ways to examine the potential influence of slice
 675 angle to the results; from top to bottom, the tilted slices represent angles 1, 2 and 3, respectively
 676 (Supplementary Table 5); DER = Dentine Exposure Ratio; EDBI = Enamel-Dentine Boundary
 677 Index; ET = Enamel Thickness.

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Supplementary Figure 8. Comparing two independently extracted micro-CT wear simulation

680

series using the same specimen (AaO-3932, UM3); Series 1 was extracted by D. Yang; series 2

681

was extracted by A. Souron; colored shades represent confidence limits of the data points; DER

682

= Dentine Exposure Ratio; EDBI = Enamel-Dentine Boundary Index; ET = Enamel Thickness.

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685 Supplementary Figure 9. Intra-specific variation of occlusal functional traits in M3s of *Sus*

686 *scrofa*. Upper M3s display consistently higher EDBI than lower M3s. DER = Dentine Exposure

687 Ratio; EDBI = Enamel-Dentine Boundary Index; ET = Enamel Thickness.

688

689 Supplementary Figure 10. Comparison between upper and lower molars in *Metridiochoerus*
 690 *shawi* and *Notochoerus scotti*. *Metridiochoerus shawi* displays similar patterns in both EDBI and
 691 ET while *Notochoerus scotti* displays higher EDBI values and lower ET in the lower M3
 692 compared to the upper M3. *Met.* = *Metridiochoerus*; *Not.* = *Notochoerus*; DER = Dentine
 693 Exposure Ratio; EDBI = Enamel-Dentine Boundary Index; ET = Enamel Thickness.

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699 Supplementary Figure 11. Morphometric measurements of functional occlusal traits based on
 700 occlusal photographs of selected fossil specimens from the Koobi Fora Formation (Early
 701 Pleistocene); gray dots represent data from the occlusal photographs using the same processing
 702 protocol presented in Appendix 2; colored shades represent the confidence limits of micro-CT
 703 based measurements presented in Figure 4 and Supplementary Figure 9; *Met.* = *Metridiochoerus*;
 704 DER = Dentine Exposure Ratio; EDBI = Enamel-Dentine Boundary Index; ET = Enamel
 705 Thickness.

706

Appendix 2: Data collection Protocols

I. Protocol for using *Avizo* to virtually simulate dental wear

1. Load the micro-CT image files with the scan specifications.

Right click on the loaded object and

select “Compute -> Resample”. This

will Set the resolution

Right click on the loaded object and

create volume rendering of the scans.

Adjust the threshold value to get rid of

padding material. This step creates a

reference for the placement of the

slices.

Right click on the original object, under

“Display” tab, find the last option

“Slice”, so that a slice object is created.

(Supplementary Figure 12)

Supplementary Figure 12

726

727 2. Click on the slice object and bring up the
728 window. Use the orientation buttons to select a
729 plane that is closest to the occlusal plane. Check the
730 options “rotate” and “adjust” so that slices can be
731 adjusted to the occlusal plane. (Supplementary
732 Figure 13)

733

734

735

736 3. Rotate the 3D rendering in the main window so
737 that the pillars are visible from either the buccal or
738 the lingual side. Use the “clip” button to hide part
739 of the volume so that the slice can be adjusted.
740 (Supplementary Figure 14)

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Supplementary Figure 13

Supplementary Figure 14

745 4. Once the slice is in display and the orientation of the tooth adjusted, use the “hand” (trackball
746 tool) to rotate the scan for better vision, and use the “arrow” (interact tool) to adjust the rotation
747 of the slice by dragging the ball frame below, indicated by the red arrow. When activated, the
748 ball frame will turn yellow and you can adjust the orientation of the slice in three different
749 directions (Supplementary Figure 15).

750

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Supplementary Figure 15

752 5. Adjust the slice to the extent that it is perpendicular to the growth axis of the cervical half of
753 the second pair of pillars (for consistency purposes), and make sure to check from multiple
754 views, including mesio-distal and bucco-lingual views (Supplementary Figure 16).

755

756

Supplementary Figure 16

757 6. Observe the simulated wear progression
758 using the “clip” button and dragging the
759 “translate” slider, as they adjust the position
760 of the slice (Supplementary Figure 17).

Supplementary Figure 17

766 7. Estimate where along the crown to start the simulation sequence and where to end. Ideally, the
767 simulated slices should have complete circles of enamel in them. But this may depend on the
768 preservation of the fossils. Two examples are given in Supplementary Figure 18.

Supplementary Figure 18

771 8. Mark down the numbers at the “translate” slider
772 for the beginning and the end of the simulation. A
773 sequence of 12-15 slices should be able to capture
774 the range of variation that is expected in the
775 progression of wear. With careful calculation,
776 evenly spaced slices can be created by entering the
777 slice position in the “translate” box.

Supplementary Figure 19

779 9. Right click on the “slice” object and select
780 “extract image” (Supplementary Figure 19). A new object (Oblique slice) will appear on the
781 main panel.

782
783 10. Right click on the “Oblique-slice”
784 object and use the option “Geometry
785 transforms -> Resample transformed
786 image”. This will create a new object
787 through which the slice will be
788 resampled based on the micro-CT scan

Supplementary Figure 20

789 (Supplementary Figure 20). This would
790 allow the extracted image to be at the same voxel resolution as the scan. Set the Reference to the
791 original scan object and click “Apply”.

792 11. Right click on the resampled oblique slice object and select “save data as...”. Select the .tif
793 format to be used in photoshop and Fiji. Go back to the slice object and enter a new number in
794 the “translate” box to create a new image. Repeat this step to export the entire sequence.

795 II. Protocol for using *Adobe Photoshop* to process an exported image

796 1. Before making any changes to the original image, save the image in a new folder.

797 2. Use the “lasso” tool from the tool bar to carefully
798 crop out an area of enamel. Toggle between the
799 circled selection tools to add or subtract from the
800 existing selected area until the entire enamel area is
801 selected. (Supplementary Figure 21) This step takes
802 time and patience.

803 Supplementary Figure 21

804 3. Once the entire enamel area is selected, right click on the selection and choose “save
805 selection” (Supplementary Figure 22). It will be saved as a channel under the “Channels”
806 window, which can be selected from the “Window” tab on the top row of the screen. You can
807 choose to activate the selection (Ctrl + Left Click channel) and modify it further any time
808 (Supplementary Figure 23). Make sure to save the selection again after modification is made.

817 Supplementary Figure 22

Supplementary Figure 23

818 4. Under the Image tab, switch the image
819 mode into RGB color and 8 bits
820 (Supplementary Figure 24). Activate the
821 saved selection (from channels) holding
822 down the Ctrl button and left click on the
823 channel that has all the enamel in it. Create
824 a new layer via copy, activate the saved
825 channel, hide the background layer, then use
826 the delete button
827 to clear this layer (with the selection still be activated).

Supplementary Figure 24

829 5. Use the “pencil” tool to color this layer as pink (#fb6469ff).
830 Now the colored area represents enamel area (Supplementary
831 Figure 25). Save this as Layer 1.

Supplementary Figure 25

834 6. Create a new layer (Layer 2) and place this layer on top of the Layer 1. Select Layer 1 and
835 activate the “magic wand” tool. Toggle to the “Add to
836 Selection function” (Supplementary Figure 26).
837 Check the Anti-Alias box. Select all areas within the
838 enamel that are representative of the dentine.

Supplementary Figure 26

841 7. Select Layer 2 and activate the pencil tool. Change the
842 color to red (#fa0019ff) for representation of dentin. With the
843 selection from Layer 1 still active, color this selection. Now
844 the colored area represents dentine area (Supplementary
845 Figure 27).

846
847
848 Supplementary Figure 27

849 8. If there are areas of cementum, select Layer 2 and activate the magic wand tool and toggle to
850 the “Add to Selection” option. Select all the areas of cementum and “delete” these areas from
851 Layer 2. Create a new layer (Layer 3) and place it on top of Layer 2. With the
852 selection still activated, color in the areas using the pencil tool in a dark red color
853 (#96000aff).

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855
856
857 Supplementary Figure 28

858 10. The end result should be the same as shown in Figure 6: clear background,
859 pink enamel area, red dentine area and dark red cementum area. (Supplementary
860 Figure 29)

861
862
863 Supplementary Figure 29

864 III. Protocol for using *Fiji* to make measurements

865 1. Make sure that the images are 8-bit RGB. If not, save them as 8-bit RGB in *Photoshop*.

866 2. Set the scale of the image to the scale on record (Analyze -> Set scale). Set distance in pixels
867 to 1, set known distance to “pixel size” in the .info file, and set unit of length to mm.

868 3. Go to image -> adjust -> color threshold. Then drag the slider of brightness until the entire
869 occlusal area is highlighted (Saturation: 1 – 255; Brightness: 0 – 255). Hit the select button so
870 that the outline of the area is highlighted.

871 4. Under Analyze -> Set measurement, check the “area” and “perimeter” boxes.

872 5. Use Analyze -> measure (Ctrl + M) to make measurements of the occlusal area.

873 6. Go back to the threshold window and adjust the brightness and saturation slider until the area
874 represents only dentine (Saturation: 255 – 255; Brightness: 255 – 255). Make sure that darker
875 cementum areas are NOT included. Then hit the select button to highlight.

876 7. Use Analyze -> measure (Ctrl + M) to make measurements of the dentine area.

877 8. Go back to the threshold window and adjust the brightness and saturation slider until the area
878 represents only cementum (Saturation: 1 – 255; Brightness: 0 – 153). Then hit the select button
879 to highlight.

880 9. Use Analyze -> measure (Ctrl + M) to make measurements of the cementum area.

881 10. Go back to the threshold window and adjust the brightness and saturation slider until the area
882 represents only enamel (Saturation: 1 – 254; Brightness: 0 – 255). Then hit the select button to
883 highlight.

884 11. Use Analyze -> measure (Ctrl + M) to make measurements of the cementum area. Copy all
885 the measured values to a spreadsheet. End of measuring one processed image.

886